

S I N G L E

D3.3 Stack delivery

WP3, T3.2

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Technical references

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Executive summary

First stack was assembled by CTMS in M6. Stack P2-66-037 is a reference stack to be used for equipment commissioning and establishment of a baseline performance. The stack has been through standard QC tests during the manufacture process, and the parameters are evaluated to be within an acceptable tolerance range.

DOCUMENT HISTORY:

v	Date	Author(s)	Description
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1.0	10.11.2023	Selene Hernández Morejudo (CTMS)	Final version

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1. Scope

T3.2 will deliver stacks for testing in T3.4, T3.5 and WP4. Activities for improving performance and tolerance to relevant conditions are planned in WP1 and WP2, and validated improvements will be implemented in future stacks. D3.3 is limited to delivery of a first reference stack for establishing a baseline test and tuning test conditions. It is therefore based on the pre-existing design from CTMS, and will serve to establish a baseline for future design. A reactor with a reference stack consists of the components described in the Table 1, and the stacking is illustrated in the Figure 1.

Table 1: Parts list for reference reactor

Component	# of parts per stack
Top reactor lid	1
Bottom reactor lid	1
Reactor tube	1
Electrical feedthrough	2
Gas ports	4
Electrical connector	1
Gradient connector	2
Connector seals	2
Top manifold	1
Bottom manifold	1
Interconnect plate	5
Sealing gasket	6
Face seal ring	36
Conductive washer	36
Membrane tube	36

Figure 1: Reference reactor and stack assembly.

2. First reference stack delivered

A reference stack with stack ID: P2-66-037 was assembled in M6 by CTMS for testing in T3.5 by CSIC. The stack awaits assembly into reactor housing and shipment to CSIC for logistics coordination. All parts are in stock.

Materials specification list and a picture of stack P2-66-037 is given below.

Table 2: Materials specification of reference stack.

Stack component	Material specification
Cell	Ni-BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} support electrode BaZr _{0.8} Ce _{0.1} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} electrolyte Ni-BaZr _{0.7} Ce _{0.2} Y _{0.1} O _{3-δ} outer electrode
Face seal	GC594
Gasket seal	GC654
Conductive washer	Ni-GC593
Interconnect/Bottom manifold	Ni-GC657
Current collector	Nickel
Electrical contacting	Copper wire
Top manifold	ZTA with ferritic header
Reactor housing	HT 800

Figure 2: Picture of stack PP-66-0037.

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3. Quality tracking

The delivered stack has undergone all standard process- and quality-control (QC) steps during its production.

All components going into the stack are verified to be within tolerances. In-house manufactured parts like membranes, barrels and the final stack are passed through critical to quality (CTQ) control steps to filter out any out of spec parts. This ensures sufficiently low leak rates, few electric defects, and accurate geometries.

Below is a summary of some of the CTQ values from the QC of stack P2-66-037.

Table 3: CTQ values for stack P2-66-037.

P2-66-037	Value	Tolerance
Internal stack leak rate ($\Delta P = 1$ bar)	1.4 mbar L/s	< 2 mbar L/s
Inter barrel short-circuits	2	< 3
Inter barrel contact loss	0	0
Shell hermiticity	Not welded	< 0.1 mbar L/s

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